

PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF HOSPITAL SCHOOL AND HOME EDUCATION

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Abstract. *In this study, we present information about the processes of providing education to students with learning difficulties due to disabilities and illnesses in hospital and home education. Based on this information, the history of hospital education and the opinions of experienced pedagogical psychologists on hospital education were analyzed. Guidelines are given for the development of pedagogical methods used in providing education to students in hospital schools and home education.*

Keywords: *Hospital school, home education, pedagogical methods, student with disabilities, psychological interview.*

GOSPITAL MAKTAB VA UY TA'LIMINING PEDAGOGIK ASOSLARI

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqotda biz Gospital va uy ta'limi asosida nogironligi, kasalligi tufayli ta'lim olishda muammoli o'quvchilarga ta'lim berish jarayonlari haqida ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tilgan. Bu ma'lumotlarga asoslangan holda gospital ta'limini tarixi va gospital ta'lim bo'yicha tajribali pedagog-psixologlarning fikrlari tahlil qilib borilgan. Gospital maktab va uy ta'limida bo'lgan o'quvchilarga bilim berishda foydalaniladigan pedagogik metodlar ishlab chiqish bo'yicha ko'rsatmalar beriladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Gospital maktab, uy ta'limi, pedagogik metodlar, nogironligi bo'lgan o'quvchi, psixologik suhbat.*

**ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ГОСПИТАЛЬНОЙ ШКОЛЫ И ДОМАШНЕГО
ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ**

Аннотация. *В данном исследовании мы представляем информацию о процессах предоставления образования учащимся, испытывающим трудности в обучении из-за инвалидности и болезней, на основе обучения в больнице и на дому. На основе этой информации были проанализированы история больничного образования и мнения опытных педагогов-психологов по поводу больничного образования. Даются инструкции по разработке педагогических методов, которые можно использовать при обучении студентов в больничных школах и на дому.*

Ключевые слова: Больничная школа, домашнее образование, педагогические методы, учащийся с ограниченными возможностями, психологическое интервью.

Introduction

Hospital schools are a means of guaranteeing the right to education for adolescents with chronic disabilities and illnesses, providing them with education from a teacher during periods of frequent treatment and prolonged hospital stays. The hospital school is recognized as part of a therapeutic program in the medical field, driven by the need to offer hospitalized students the same opportunities to acquire skills and knowledge as their peers. The issue of integrating "students affected by pathologies" into society has been considered increasingly urgent over the years, especially during the global pandemic.

To address this question, it is necessary to "think pedagogically in education"; that is, to develop simplified methods for hospital education based on pedagogical approaches. The hospital school program originated in Italy in the 1960s, when some special school branches were opened in pediatric departments. The aim of the Hospital School program was to help young students avoid the typical difficulties and challenges of returning to their original schools through educational and learning support from primary school teachers. It was recognized as a means of guaranteeing the right to education for schoolchildren with chronic diseases that often become disabling and require long-term treatment with long-term hospitalization or home care. Until the middle of the last century, the importance of meeting the needs of the whole child in pediatrics was not sufficiently appreciated. During long-term hospitalization, attention was focused only on managing the disease, neglecting the psychoemotional sphere of the pediatric patient. The child was removed from his environment and family, believing that he would be more calm without the constant presence of his parents.

On the contrary, this often caused depression, aggression and internal conflicts in the child, which led to changes in the development of his personality. It was Anna Freud, with her research that began in the 1930s, who first explored the world of the sick child and showed the enormous difference between the unconscious experiences of adults and the fantasies of children against illness. The main scientific evidence, which comes from the descriptions of mothers about the behavior of their children during and after illness and hospitalization, is that serious psychological changes, changes in relationships with parents and siblings, the onset of eating and sleeping disorders, the onset of apathy, enuresis, regressions or, conversely, pathological acceleration of

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behavior, are the causes. Hospitalization is always a traumatic event for children, in which doctors are unknown figures, and the younger they are, the more threatening they are.

If the illness causes anxiety in the child, hospitalization manifests itself as an uncontrolled threat to his integrity through loss of autonomy, distorted perception of time, loss of self-confidence and a feeling of abandonment. In addition, hospitalization is a stressful event that leads to changes and disruptions in normal life habits. Going to school, maintaining social relationships with peers, participating in classes and sports are certainly among the foundations of a child's life.

Consequently, the hospitalized pediatric patient inevitably feels a lack of school environment in terms of educational activities, communication with teachers and friendships with peers. Some of these children develop a specific anxiety about falling behind in completing tasks compared to their classmates, which negatively affects their performance at school.

Furthermore, hospital stays can increase the risk of students dropping out of school, for example due to lack of schooling. This is particularly important because dropping out of school can lead to early school leaving, educational failure or academic failure, such as a reduced likelihood of completing compulsory education or entering university. Finally, hospitalization can occur at important transition stages, such as starting school, or at key learning and development milestones, such as the onset of adolescence. Therefore, it is important to create a communicative framework that facilitates the child's adaptation to the new environment and establishes continuity of change. Teachers play a crucial role in such challenging situations.

They need to understand the patients' feelings, acting as a bridge between the children's small inpatient room and the outside world. In addition, teachers can support and encourage the hospitalized student's interest; when the child is interested in something, he or she "forgets" about the illness and overcomes boredom and hospital depression, especially in long-term care.

There are several key characteristics that are necessary for this role. First, it is important to be able to adapt to the rescheduled programs and goals, depending on the number of patients, their different levels of learning, the severity of their symptoms, and the duration of their hospitalization.

Given the complexity of this educational scenario, teachers opt for an individual approach and sometimes work in small groups. In contrast to what happens in the classroom, the teacher working in a hospital seeks to modulate the educational offer according to the complex cognitive-emotional flow of the hospitalized student and to stimulate learning with the aim of personalization. In fact, rather than pursuing predetermined and standardized cognitive goals, the teacher identifies with the student ways to enhance all aspects of the child and his overall well-being.

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These ways can see the teacher and the hospital school as protagonists of the "educational agency", of the "mediation" between being a child and the reality of the hospital environment in which he lives.

Hospital teachers must organize their educational activities around the physical health and psychological well-being of the students, as well as the needs arising from the experience of illness and isolation. An important condition for teaching effectiveness is, of course, planning; from a practical point of view, teachers: The teacher is involved in the careful and constant work of receiving, decoding and responding to the signals emitted by the sick child - even if not explicitly, but equally important. This requires intentional "listening" and real interaction with the sick child.

In addition, there is a constant need to identify and overcome any communication disorders of a "contextual", psychological or physiological nature, which are associated with the state of anxiety or fear of the hospitalized child, his sense of inadequacy or inadequacy, the desire for distraction or the need for solitude. Such "Psychological conversation", if not clearly identified and eliminated, contributes to the breakdown of communication with the hospitalized child. In short, it is necessary to have a deep connection with the pain and suffering of patients and their families, to develop a trusting relationship with each other. Another aspect of the complexity of the hospital situation was assessed as the relationship with the parents, who, together with the medical team, regulate the rhythm of the patient's child's life and establish order. Thanks to the communicative skills of teachers, it is possible to establish harmony in relationships and create a calm atmosphere necessary for the child to overcome the disruptions in his previous life and perceive the reality of the hospital as only a transitional stage.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the advances made by modern medicine in the last few decades mean that complex diseases that often have fatal consequences can now be better managed, resulting in many pediatric patients who are able to return to school. However, the condition of recovery is sometimes achieved after a long and arduous journey, which often leaves the patient psychologically traumatized. This problem becomes even more demanding when the subject is a minor, since children and adolescents experience the state of illness differently than adults. It would be convenient for students to consider their hospital experience as a period without deprivation and fear, but with its own meaning and value: it is appropriate to provide psychological support based on the enriching experiences that children and families add to the life story, as well as to society, classmates and teachers.

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